

Parameter identification of variable stiffness actuators for a humanoid robot

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I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, robots with elastic joints have been attracting increasing interest in the robotics community. Some of the main advantages introduced by elastic joints are the ability to interact safely with humans and the remarkable adaptability to environmental changes. ALTER-EGO [4], a humanoid robot born from the joint efforts of the Italian Institute of Technology and the Research Center “E. Piaggio” of the University of Pisa, belongs to this category. It is a robust and versatile mobile system with a functional anthropomorphic upper body which boasts six degrees of freedom for each arm. Both are driven by variable stiffness actuators, whose operation is inspired by that of a pair of human muscles. In the real world, elastic actuators are susceptible to wear and tear over time, which can lead to changes in their parameters.

This paper presents a parameter identification method based on the estimation of the actual elastic torque through the residual method [2], aimed at improving control accuracy.

II. PARAMETER IDENTIFICATION

Variable Stiffness Actuators are an innovative class of robotic actuators that can adjust their stiffness in response to environmental or task-specific requirements. Characterized by the use of two motors and springs, VSAs allow both the shaft and the stiffness position to be adjusted according to the configuration assumed. Those used in the arms of ALTER-EGO fall into the category of “Bidirectional A-A design”. This layout is inspired by the way human muscles operate. Two motors connected through elastic elements to the output shaft are used to transmit the desired position and stiffness.

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The expression of the total elastic torque developed by these actuators is:

$$\tau_{el} = k_1 \sinh(a_1(-q + \theta_1)) + k_2 \sinh(a_2(-q + \theta_2)) \quad (1)$$

where q is the shaft output position, θ_1 and θ_2 represent the two motors position, and k_1, k_2, a_1, a_2 are the elastic parameters of the springs.

Fig. 1: The ALTER-EGO variable stiffness humanoid robot performing a service task in an office environment.

Although model (1) has been shown to fit experimental torque data pretty well [1], the knowledge of the four parameters $k_1, a_1, k_2,$ and a_2 is subject to uncertainty because of production spread and wear. This, in turn, can severely undermine control performance.

Therefore, we aim to estimate the value of such parameters. However, to give a good estimate, one needs to measure the elastic torque τ_{el} . That is not possible on ALTER-EGO, because it doesn’t have joint torque sensors.

Thus, we propose to identify those parameters by relying on an estimate of τ_{el} based on the residual method [2].

A. The Residual Method

The residual method [2] is a numerically robust technique to estimate joint torques, based on an accurate dynamic model of the robot. Starting from Lagrange’s equations for a mechanical system with n degrees of freedom, we build the residual r as

$$r = a [B\dot{q} + \int(G - X - r)dt], \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2: Residual-based elastic torque estimation in simulation.

where $B = B(q)$ is the robot inertia matrix, $G = G(q)$ is the vector of gravitational torques, and

$$X = X(q, \dot{q}) = \frac{1}{2} \dot{q}^T \frac{\partial B(q) \dot{q}}{\partial q}. \quad (3)$$

As it is shown in [2], that yields a low-pass filter of the torque input to the robot joints (in our case the elastic torque τ_{el}), as

$$r = \frac{a}{s + a} \tau_{el}. \quad (4)$$

Figure 2 shows the performance of such method on a simulated version of ALTER-EGO, built with the framework described in [5].

B. Implementation Details

A numerical optimization was performed in MATLAB, through the `fmincon` function, by minimizing the Mean Square Error between the elastic torque (1) and the residual.

The derivative of $B(q)$ in X was implemented numerically via the forward finite difference method.

Discretization was carried out by Euler's forward method.

C. Results

Looking at Figure 3 it can be observed that the error between the elastic torque computed with the identified parameters and the residual is significantly lower than the one between the residual and the initial guess of the elastic torque. It is indeed possible to see how the elastic torque with identified parameters more closely matches the behavior of the residual.

Figure 4 shows the tracking performance on ALTER-EGO's elbow joint with nominal and identified parameters when executing a trajectory recorded in tele-operation.

III. CONCLUSIONS

The parameter identification method presented in this paper demonstrates a significant improvement in the control accuracy of variable stiffness actuators. By leveraging a residual-based approach, elastic parameters have been identified, reducing the error between the actual and the estimated elastic torque. The ability to account for changes in actuator dynamics over time ensures long-term robustness in real-world applications.

Fig. 3: Elastic torque with identified parameters in blue, Residual in red and Elastic torque with nominal parameters in green

Fig. 4: Desired position in red, measured position with nominal parameters in blue, measured position with identified parameters in magenta

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